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Molluscicidal activity and genotoxic effects of some pesticides and plant powders against the land snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae)

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Abstract

The molluscicidal activity and genotoxic effects of six synthetic pesticides (Neomyl, Gastrotox, Lampada, thymol, Malathion, and Aphold) and four plant powders (oleander, castor bean, clove buds and thyme) were investigated on *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) snails. The mortality percentage of snails increased with higher concentrations and longer exposure periods for both pesticides and plant powders. The general mean of mortality percentage at concentration 8% could be arranged in descending order as follows: 71.1, 67.82, 67.21, 59.4, 51.64, and 15.51% for Lampada, Thymol, Neomyl, Malathion, Gastrotox, and Aphold, respectively. Among the plant powders, the general means at 40% concentration were highest for clove buds, followed by castor bean, oleander, and thyme, respectively. In addition, genotoxic effects of the tested substances were evaluated. Among the synthetic pesticides, Neomyl treatments had the highest effect on DNA fragmentation. Generally, plant material treatments resulted in less DNA fragmentation than pesticides, except clove buds, which caused high damage levels almost as high as the effect of pesticides. These findings suggest that tested pesticides could induce residual and latent effects more than plant powders, which may cause lower residual and latent effects. DNA fragmentation is a known marker of apoptosis and may be a response to the excessive accumulation of toxic substances. These findings demonstrated that the plant-based pesticide exhibited low residual activity and a comparable latent effect, aligning with the principles of sustainable integrated pest management.

Introduction

Recently, it has become essential to focus on the increasing use of different

types of agrochemicals and pesticides in ecosystems that could pose a severe public health problem and a threat to

the environment. In the case of land snails, scientists recommended pesticides, especially on large-scale farms during high snail populations. As a standard control strategy, the most common snail control methods involve using chemical bait pellets containing metaldehyde or carbamates (Henderson and Triebkorn, 2002). Thus, Daoud (2004) reported that Neomyl exhibited the highest toxic action against *Monacha* sp. snails. The land snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) is economically widely distributed all over the world (Feldkamp, 2002), causing several damages in cultivated and newly reclaimed agroecosystems. The last studies indicated that this snail was the most abundant in all localities in Egypt (Mahrous *et al.*, 2002; Abou Senna *et al.*, 2016 and Ismail *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, Amal *et al.* (2019) recommended certain chemicals and methomyl against the land snail *Monacha* sp. In the last decade, the use of natural products for pest control has greatly increased. Plant-based pesticides and phytochemicals have received much effort as prospective safe, useful bioactive compounds to replace the other synthetic pesticides (Isman and Grieneisen, 2014 and Rapado *et al.*, 2011). In the same trend, Abdel-Rahman (2017) reported the efficiency of some natural plant extracts in controlling the land snail (*M. cartusiana*).

Further, assessing the activity and safety of pesticides and their natural alternatives involves carrying out a variety of tests that can measure toxicity at different levels. These tests can range from measuring the reduction of pest populations and survival analyses (Rady *et al.*, 2018, and Maarooof *et al.*, 2023) to assessing physiological abnormalities such as tissue damage and enzymatic disturbance (Fong and Ford, 2014, and

Atlam *et al.*, 2023). Recently, assays at the molecular level have also been used to assess genotoxicity, which can involve testing for chromatin fragmentation/condensation and DNA damage using methods such as comet, DNA fragmentation, and DAPI staining assays. The ordered DNA fragment pattern observed in agarose gel electrophoresis was identified as the biochemical feature of apoptosis; it is considered one of the most dependable methods for the detection of DNA damage caused by toxicants or pollutants (Eskandani *et al.*, 2013 and 2014). As far as the use of toxic and genotoxic chemicals in ecosystems, it has raised concerns about their impact on the health of nearby populations. To address this issue, this study compared the safety and effectiveness of specific pesticides and natural alternatives (such as plant powders). The molluscicidal activity of these substances was tested on *M. cartusiana* snails using common toxicity and genotoxicity assays.

Materials and methods

1. Tested pesticides:

Some commercial pesticides belonging to different chemical groups were used to evaluate the molluscicidal activity against the land snail *M. cartusiana*. The tested pesticides were Neomyl (Methomyl 20%), Lampada (Cyhalothrine), Thymol (2-Isopropyl-5methylphenol), Uphold (Spinetoram), Malathion (2-Dimethoxyphosphinothioylthiobutanedioic acid diethyl ester), and Gastrotax (Metaldehyde 5%).

2. Plant materials:

The full data about the plants selected for this work are listed in Table (1). The oleander leaves and castor bean were collected and then dried in the shade for two weeks. The dried leaves and kernels were roasted in an oven at 45°C. for 48 hrs. Also, clove buds and thyme leaves, which were bought from

the market, were roasted too in the same conditions as before. All plant materials were ground in a steel grinder

separately until they became fine powder.

Table (1): Plant powder investigated for molluscicidal activity against.

English Name	Scientific Name	Used Part	Location
Oleander	<i>Nerium oleander</i>	Leaves	Zagazig district, Sharqia, Egypt
Castor bean	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Seeds	Hehia district, Sharqia, Egypt
Clove buds	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Buds	Local market
Thyme	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Leaves	Local market

3. Application technique:

Poisonous baits of each compound were prepared by mixing four tested concentrations (1, 2, 4, and 8%) of each pesticide with bran to complete (100 parts) of poisonous baits, and adequate water was added to it. About 25mg of poisonous bait was spread into plastic boxes, and ten healthy adult snails of *M. cartusiana* were introduced to each box. Three replicates were used for each treatment, as well as a control treatment being prepared in the same manner without any pesticides. Boxes were covered with muslin cloth and banding with plastic rubber to prevent land snails from escaping (Ismail *et al.*, 2010). The poisonous baits of plant powders were prepared in the same manner as before (Ismail *et al.*, 2010), but with three concentrations of each powder (10, 20, and 40 %) added to wheat bran. The experiment was carried out and maintained in the same conditions as before. All boxes were examined after 1, 3, 7-, 14-, 21-, and 28-days post-treatment. Dead snails were counted and removed from boxes. Mortality percentages were calculated and corrected using Abbott's formula (1925) as follows:
 Percent control $(X-Y / X) \times 100$
 X: the percent living in the check.
 Y: the percent living in the treated plate.

Then $X - Y$: the percent killed by the treatment.

4. DNA fragmentation analysis:

DNA extraction was operated according to the methods of Phillips and Simon (1995) with some modifications as follows: One gastropod, about 50 mg, was put in a one ml microfuge tube. 600 μ l of extraction buffer (1.5 M NaCl, 100 mM Tris-Cl (pH 8.8), 50 mM EDTA, 5% CTAB) was added, tissues were crushed in the buffer till dispersed, and 2 μ l of proteinase-K solution (10 mg/ml) was added. Tubes were incubated at 56°C overnight with occasional vigorous mixing. After incubation, the DNA solution was washed with a mixture of 600 μ l phenol, chloroform, and isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1); then, the samples were inverted several times and centrifuged for 5 min at 6000 rpm. The 400-500 μ l upper aqueous layer of each sample was transferred carefully into a new tube containing 900 μ l of water and 100 μ l of exchange buffer (CTAB 5%, 0.4M NaCl). The mixture was set for two min. at room temperature and then spun at 6000 rpm for 15 min. The supernatant was discarded, 300 ml of 1.2 M NaCl was added, and the mixture was shaken gently, followed by the addition of 750 μ l of absolute ethanol, inverted to mix and left to set at -20°C overnight for DNA

precipitation. Then centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 20 min., and pellets were then washed with 250 µl of 70% ethanol and spun again. The supernatants were discarded; pellets were left to air dry, and 50 µl of Tris-EDTA buffer was added and then left to set at 37°C overnight till completely dissolved. The “DNA fragmentation assay” method described by Bortner *et al.* (1995) was carried out. Samples were electrophoresed on a 1.2% agarose gel at a low voltage (50 volts), which improves the resolution of DNA fragments and the gel was stained using ethidium bromide.

The analysis of the agarose gel image was determined using Gel Analyzer Software. (Version 19.1) by GelAnalyzer.com.

<http://www.gelanalyzer.com/?i=1>.

Results and discussion

The effects of six compounds: Neomyl, Gastrotox, Lampada, Thymol, Malathion, and Aphold against *M. cartusiana* snails as poison baits under laboratory conditions are tabulated in Table (2). Generally, results showed that the mortality percentage fluctuated according to different treatments. Moreover, the mortality percentage increased with the increase in the concentrations and exposure periods. All tested compounds failed to exhibit any molluscicidal activity at one day post-treatment. The mortality values were recorded with Neomyl, Gastrotox, Lampada, Thymol, and Malathion at a concentration of 8% after 3 days of treatment. The recorded values were 36.6, 26.6, 83.33, 33.33, and 46.6%, respectively. While the general means of these compounds were 67.21, 51.64, 71.1, 67.82, and 59.4, respectively. The lowest effect was

recorded with the treatment of Aphold at a concentration of 8%, which recorded 15.51 as a general mean. Regarding the general means, we can arrange the efficiency of the tested pesticides deridingly as follows: Lampada, Thymol, Neomyl, Malathion, Gastrotox, and Aphold.

More machine findings by Ghaly *et al.* (2009) found the general means of reduction percentages of pesticides used under field conditions. El-Akhrasy (2010) reported that metaldehyde at 5% gave a high mortality percentage (100%) after 3 days post-treatment against *M. cartusiana*. Al-Sarar *et al.* (2012) claimed that organophosphorus and pyrethroid pesticides are not effective against land snails and are not used to combat them. Likewise, methomyl, methiocarb, and metaldehyde are used to control land snails in the form of baits containing high concentrations of active ingredients. Results of El-Akhrasy (2017) arranged the compounds descending by their efficacy against *E. vermiculata* as follows: Amino, Humic acid, Cyflumagic, Micronized sulfur, Fusillade, k-othrine WG250, Potassium thiosulfate, Urea, and combed Zn compared with Neomyl, and against *M. cartusiana* as follows: Amino, humic acid, Fusillade, cyflumagic, urea, combined Zn, potassium thiosulfate, and k-othrine WG250 compared with Neomyl. Rady *et al.* (2018) revealed that *M. Obstructa* was the most susceptible of *Eobania vermiculata* (Muller) and *Helicella vestalis* (Pfeiffer) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) for the adult exposed to Lambda-Cyhalothrin. On the other hand, immature stages exhibited altered responses to Lambda-Cyhalothrin than adults.

Table (2): Mortality percentages of some compounds against *Monacha cartusiana* snails under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Conc. %	Cumulative mortality percentages after indicated days						General means
		1 day	3 days	7 days	14 days	21 days	28 days	
Neomyl	1	0	10	26.66	46.66	60	70.33	35.6 ^j
	2	0	16	33.33	49	66.33	73.66	39.72 ⁱ
	4	0	26.6	46.66	76.66	80	80	51.65 ^g
	8	0	36.6	80	86.66	100	100	67.21 ^b
Lampada	1	0	0	0	0	0	6.66	1.11 ^r
	2	0	3.33	10	20	36.6	40	18.32 ^m
	4	0	60	76.66	86.66	86.66	86.66	66.1 ^c
	8	0	83.33	83.33	86.66	86.66	86.66	71.1 ^a
Thymol	1	0	0	3.33	6.66	16.66	56.66	13.88 ^p
	2	0	16.6	33.3	46	76.33	100	45.37 ^h
	4	0	30	46	86.66	100	100	60.44 ^d
	8	0	33.33	73.6	100	100	100	67.82 ^b
Malathion	1	0	10	10	10	10	16.6	9.43 ^a
	2	0	10	40	46.6	50	60	34.43 ^k
	4	0	30	56.6	73.3	80	86.6	54.41 ^f
	8	0	46.6	63.3	76.6	83.3	86.6	59.4 ^c
Aphold	1	0	0	0	0	0	6.6	1.1 ^r
	2	0	0	0	13.3	40	53.3	17.7 ^{mn}
	4	0	0	0	16.6	33.3	36.6	14.4 ^p
	8	0	0	3.3	16.6	36.6	36.6	15.51 ^o
Gastrotox	1	0	6.66	16.66	20	26.6	33.33	17.2 ⁿ
	2	0	10	26.6	36.66	46	63.3	30.42 ^l
	4	0	13.3	33.3	40	66.6	86.6	39.96 ⁱ
	8	0	26.6	46.66	56.6	80	100	51.64 ^g
LSD _{0.05}								0.61 ^{***}

Values in columns followed by different letters are significant at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

The effect of the four plants' powder against *M. cartusiana* under laboratory conditions is shown in Table (3). Results revealed that the mortality percentage increased with increasing concentration and exposure periods. Further, all tested materials failed to exhibit any molluscicidal activity against *M. cartusiana* snails on the first day post-treatment with all concentrations (10, 20, and 40%). The low concentration (10%) of four plant powders induced the minimum mortality after 3 days of treatment, while the lowest mortality percentages at all were recorded by Clove buds and Thyme, respectively, as 3.33 and 3.33%. Also, after 7 days of treatment, the same concentration of 10% of Clove buds and Thyme powders induced the minimum mortality of snails compared with others. On the other hand, the

highest concentration of 40% induced the medium mortality percentages for *M. cartusiana* snails after 28 days of treatment, where the highest mortality percentage was 66.33, 56.33, 100, and 36.33% for oleander, castor oil plant, clove buds, and thyme, respectively.

Generally, the mortality percentages increased with increasing plant powder concentration and time elapsed. It can be concluded that the snail *M. cartusiana*. On the 7th day post treatment, clove buds caused the highest mortality percentage, giving 90% with the concentration of 40% while oleander caused the lowest percentage (16.66). As time elapsed, mortality percentages increased by increasing concentration until reaching 100% for clove buds, while thyme recorded the lowest one (36.33) 28 days post-treatment. General means of these

plant powders (Oleander, castor bean, clove buds, and thyme) at a concentration of 40%, were recorded (30.49, 33.22, 56.11, and 21.05), respectively. So, we could arrange the plants according to their activities as follows: clove buds, castor bean, oleander, and thyme. These findings were in the same context as many studies; Lokma (2007) showed that juveniles and adults of *M. cartusiana*, in Cactus leaves and Blue scarlet pimpernel, mixed leaves, stems, and flowers against *M. cartusiana*, and they didn't have any molluscicidal activity

under both laboratory conditions. More agrees with those of Kumar and Singh (2006), who found that the toxicity of *Syzygium aromaticum* flower-bud powder (96 hrs. LC₅₀ = 51.98 mg/L) was more pronounced against the freshwater snail, *Liminea acuminata* Lamarck (Gastropoda: Lymnaeidae). Ismail and Abdel-Kader (2011) recorded a high mortality percentage; over 80% were obtained with clove buds, bud powder, and eugenol for juvenile and adult snails 21days after treatment.

Table (3): Mortality percentage of four plants against *Monacha cartusiana* snails under laboratory conditions.

Plant powder	Conc. %	Cumulative mortality percentages after indicated days						General means
		1 day	3 days	7 days	14 days	21 days	28 days	
Oleander	10	0	0	3.33	33.33	50	56.66	23.88 ^h
	20	0	0	6.66	36.66	50	60	25.55 ^g
	40	0	0	16.66	43.33	56.66	66.33	30.49 ^d
Castor seeds	10	0	0	20	46.66	53.33	53.33	28.88 ^f
	20	0	0	23.33	46.66	53.33	56.66	29.99 ^e
	40	0	3.33	33.33	50	56.33	56.33	33.22 ^c
Clove buds	10	0	3.33	6.66	23.33	23.33	40	16.1 ^k
	20	0	6.66	43.33	53.33	56.66	76.66	39.44 ^b
	40	0	50	90	96.66	96.66	100	72.22 ^a
Thyme	10	0	3.33	10	13.33	20	23.33	11.66 ^l
	20	0	6.66	16.66	30	30	33.33	19.44 ^j
	40	0	6.66	23.33	30	30	36.33	21.05 ⁱ
LSD 0.05								0.33***

Values in columns followed by different letters are significant at P≤0.05 according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Farag (2012) found that mortality percentages in *M. cartusiana* juveniles increased with increasing concentrations of castor oil (fresh and expired) to 93.33% and 86.67% at 60% of castor oil. Mourad (2014) indicated that the ethanol crude extract of cumin was the most toxic extract for the two tested land snail species, *E. vermiculata* and *M. obstructa*, followed by golden shower, umbrella tree, and pomegranate extracts, while olive extracts had the lowest effect. The land snail, *E. vermiculata*, was

comparatively less sensitive to the tested plant extracts than the land snail *M. obstructa*. Mobarak *et al.* (2015) indicated that the crude plant extract gave satisfying results compared with methomyl, which gave 74.5% population reduction compared with 94.4% for methomyl, respectively. Also, Farag (2012) found that mortality percentages in *M. cartusiana* juveniles increased with increasing concentrations of castor oil (fresh and expired) to 93.33% and 86.67% at 60% of castor oil.

DNA damage in treated snails:

The DNA was isolated from individual snails treated with the tested pesticides (Aphold, Malathion, Neomyl, Lambda, and Gastrotax) along with plant powders of clove buds, castor, oleander, and thyme. The effect on DNA was evaluated as levels of genomic DNA fragmentation through detecting DNA laddering on agarose gel electrophoresis (Figure 1) compared to the control group after 72 hrs. post-treatments. The results obtained from (Figure 1) revealed that all pesticide treatments induced marked DNA fragmentation at pesticide variable levels. Data showed a high level of DNA laddering pattern induced by Aphold and Malation (Lanes 4, 5); treatments proved to increase the DNA fragmentation which appeared as a weak smear along the lane with 3 detectable bands between (500-100 bsp), besides lacking in the genomic DNA bands. Likewise, lambda (lane 8) showed the same effect but was less effective in laddering, with a strong

smear throwing the lane. While the highest effect appeared with the DNA of neomyl treatments. (Lane 2). Consensually, Lesser DNA laddering with conservation of genomic DNA bands was observed in plant material treatments compared to pesticide samples, except for clove bud treatment (Lane 3), which revealed high damage levels almost reaching the effect of pesticides, followed by thyme (Lane 11) and oleander (Lane 10), respectively. Whilst castor and thymol (Lanes 6, 9) showed nearly the same laddering, this may be related to apoptotic lysis. These results may confirm the high susceptibility of the tested snails and predict residual and latent effects with a low probability of surviving against the tested pesticides, contrary to plant powders that could induce low residual and latent effects. Moreover, Gastrox showed clear laddering, and the high density of the genomic DNA band induced a low effect on DNA.

Figure (1): Analysis of DNA fragmentation of Genomic DNA isolated from gastropods of pesticide' treated snails compared with untreated sample snail; analyzed by 2% agarose gel electrophoresis followed by ethidium bromide staining. Lane (L), 1000 bp ladder. Lanes 1-11: express DNA of untreated control sample (1) and samples treated with different pesticides as follows: Neomyl (2), Aphold (4), Malathion (5), Metaldehyde (7), Lambda (8), and Thymol (9), while samples treated with plant powders as clove buds (3), castor (6), oleander (10), and thyme (11).

It is known that internucleosomal fragmentation is one of the signs of apoptosis. It can be a response to an excessive accumulation of toxic material (Creagh *et al.*, 2000), which affects the balance of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Thévenod, 2009) responsible for the inhibition of enzymes involved in DNA synthesis and repair. Further, the DNA fragmentation assay on mollusks was discussed in a few studies. Mohamed *et al.* (2012) concluded that the tested pesticides, Colchicine and Selecron, have deleterious effects on *Biomphalaria alexandrina* (Ehrenberg) (Gastropoda: Planorbidae) snails, their reproductive rate, their eggs, and the intensities of DNA and RNA in their ovotestis and digestive gland complex.

Also, DNA electrophoretic patterns of hermaphrodite-digestive glands of non-infected and *Schistosoma mansoni* infected *Biomphalaria alexandrina* snails with Mirazid showed DNA damage in hermaphrodite-digestive glands. And concluded the promising molluscicidal activity of Mirazid on *B. Alexandrina* snails (Osman *et al.*, 2014). The DNA fragmentation caused by pesticides was examined by Heikal *et al.* (2014) in testis tissues collected from Methomyl-treated rats. Methomyl expressed more bands of damaged DNA compared with untreated rats. Also, the deltamethrin pesticide recorded neurotoxicity detected as DNA fragmentation in brain cell rates (Galal *et al.*, 2014).

On the other hand, in terms of the kinetics of the fragmentation, Baurand *et al.* (2014) stated that the detection sensitivity of the DNA laddering method is low in the embryonic tissues of *B. alexandrina* snails, which are exposed to cadmium (Cd) levels, and this method can detect only a very high level of DNA damage. While Agnello *et al.* (2006) found DNA fragmentation in *P. lividus* after 38 hrs. of exposure to

CdCl₂ and considered this DNA damage to represent a final event in the induction of apoptosis.

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